

Kinetics of Oxidation of Allyl, Crotyl and Cinnamic Alcohols by Selenium Dioxide

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The kinetics of oxidation of allyl, crotyl and cinnamic alcohols by selenium dioxide in 80% (v/v) acetic acid - water mixture have been investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to both alcohols and selenium dioxide. The reactions are catalysed by a strong acid. Primary salt effect is negligible. The reaction rate increases with increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture. The observed order of reactivity is crotyl > allyl > cinnamic alcohol. Activation parameters have been calculated. A suitable mechanism, consistent with the experimental facts, has been suggested.

SELENIUM dioxide has been used as an oxidant in the study of kinetics of oxidation of some ketones¹⁻⁵. Similar studies with allylic alcohols are lacking, although kinetics of oxidation of these with other oxidants⁶⁻¹⁰ have been studied. In continuation of our recent work in the kinetic study of oxidation of organic compounds by selenium dioxide^{6,11-13}, we now report the results of kinetics of oxidation of allyl alcohol, crotyl alcohol and cinnamic alcohol by selenium dioxide in acetic acid - water mixture.

Experimental

Selenium dioxide (Loba), allyl alcohol (M & B), crotyl alcohol (Fluka, AG) and cinnamic alcohol (Sigma) were used. Acetic acid (S.M., GR) was purified over chromic oxide before use. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade. The stock solution of selenium dioxide was prepared in distilled water and was standardised iodometrically. The rate of reaction was determined by estimating the unreacted selenium dioxide by iodimetric method.

Stoichiometry and products: The stoichiometry of reactions under study have been determined by allowing the reaction mixture containing excess of selenium dioxide (10 times) over allylic alcohols at 60° until there was no change in selenium dioxide concentration. It is found that one mole of selenium dioxide is required for complete oxidation of two moles of allylic alcohols. The stoichiometric equation can, therefore, be written as

where, R=H, CH₃ and C₆H₅ for allyl, crotyl and cinnamic alcohols, respectively. The product

analysis shows that acrolein, crotonaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde are the products of selenium dioxide oxidation of allyl alcohol, crotyl alcohol and cinnamic alcohol, respectively. These aldehydes have been identified by preparing their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Results and Discussion

The variation in selenium dioxide concentration shows that the reactions under study are pseudo-first order in selenium dioxide. The pseudo-first order rate constants have been calculated by using integrated first order equation. The rate constants were calculated with an accuracy of 1-2% in duplicate kinetic runs (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SELENIUM DIOXIDE CONCENTRATION

[Alcohol] = 0.40 M, HOAc - Water = 80 : 20 (v/v), Tem. = 60°					
10 ³ [SeO ₂] M	2.5	5.0	7.5	10.0	20.0
10 ³ k s ⁻¹	a	b	c		
	5.38	5.98	5.87	5.86	5.95
	5.71	5.70	5.64	5.63	5.62
	2.68	2.68	2.66	2.65	2.63

a = allyl alcohol, b = crotyl alcohol, c = cinnamic alcohol. Rate constants for cinnamic alcohol are at 65° and [alcohol] = 0.80 M

The variation in alcohol concentration shows that the pseudo-first order rate constants in selenium dioxide increase with increase in the concentration of alcohol, but the ratio $k/[alcohol]$ remains constant (Table 2). The plots of $\log k$ vs $1 + \log [alcohol]$ are straight lines with approximately unit slope, indicating that the reactions under study are of first order in alcohols.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ALCOHOL CONCENTRATION
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01 \text{ M}$, HOAc—Water=80 : 20 (v/v), Temp.=60°

[Alcohol] M	Allyl alcohol		Crotyl alcohol		Cinnamic alcohol	
	10% s ⁻¹	10% [Alcohol] dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10% s ⁻¹	10% [Alcohol] dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10% s ⁻¹	10% [Alcohol] dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
	0.20	2.68	1.34	2.80	1.40	—
0.40	5.28	1.32	5.63	1.41	1.00	0.25
0.80	10.71	1.34	11.81	1.48	2.12	0.27
1.00	13.44	1.34	14.83	1.48	2.78	0.28
1.20	16.15	1.34	17.84	1.49	3.43	0.28

Effect of bisulphate and hydrogen ions: The variation in the concentration of bisulphate ions, studied by added NaHSO₄, did not produce any appreciable change in the reaction rate (Table 3). The effect of hydrogen ions on the reaction rate has been studied by carrying the reactions in presence of varying concentration of perchloric acid, but at fixed concentration of sulphuric acid. It is observed that the reaction rate increases with increasing concentration of perchloric acid (Table 4), indicating the reactions are catalysed by hydrogen ions. From these results it appears that the dependence of rate on [H⁺] is probably not simple.

In the oxidation of primary alcohols by acid bromate, it has been reported¹⁴ that the dependence of rate on [H⁺] is not simple.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF BISULPHATE ION
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01 \text{ M}$, [Alcohol]=0.40 M, [HClO₄]=1.0 M
 Temp.=60°, HOAc—Water=60 : 40 (v/v)

Alcohol	10% s ⁻¹ at [NaHSO ₄] M				
	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.50
Allyl	6.58	6.99	6.38	6.32	6.43
Crotyl	9.44	9.56	9.50	9.46	9.50
Cinnamic	5.07	5.15	5.10	5.11	5.06

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF HYDROGEN ION
 $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01 \text{ M}$, [Alcohol]=0.40 M, [H₂SO₄]=0.75 M
 Temp.=60°, HOAc—Water=60 : 40 (v/v)

Alcohol	10% s ⁻¹ at [Perchloric acid] M					
	0.00	0.50	0.75	1.0	1.5	2.0
Allyl	3.66	6.16	15.14	29.75	48.22	70.68
Crotyl	4.24	8.94	18.22	40.68	78.46	125.86
Cinnamic	2.62	4.78	7.52	17.83	24.83	38.62

Primary salt effect: The primary salt effect on the reaction rate has been studied by adding neutral salt, K₂SO₄ (0.00–0.016 M). It is observed that the primary salt effect is negligible. This fact suggests that at least one of the reactants involved in the rate determining step is a neutral molecule¹⁵.

Effect of solvent: The effect of solvent polarity on the rate of reaction has been studied by varying the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture. It is observed that increase in the percentage of acetic acid increases the reaction rate (Table 5).

Plot of $\log k$ vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ is linear, indicating the reaction to be of dipole–dipole¹⁶ type.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF PERCENTAGE OF ACETIC ACID ON REACTION RATE

$[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01 \text{ M}$, [Alcohol]=0.40 M, Temp.=60°				
Alcohol	10% s ⁻¹ at HOAc/Water ratio (v/v)			
		50-50	60-40	70-30
Allyl	2.70	3.32	4.27	5.28
Crotyl	3.10	3.70	4.49	5.63
$[\text{Cinnamic alcohol}]=0.80 \text{ M}$, $[\text{SeO}_2]=0.01 \text{ M}$, Temp.=65°				
HOAc/Water (v/v)	75-25	80-20	85-15	90-10
10% s ⁻¹	2.15	2.61	3.13	3.65

Effect of temperature: To study the effect of temperature, the kinetics of oxidation of allylic alcohols by selenium dioxide has been studied at five different temperatures. The plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ are linear. Activation parameters, such as energy of activation (ΔE), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*), entropy of activation (ΔS^*) and free energy of activation (ΔG^*) have been evaluated. The calculated values are recorded together in Table 6.

TABLE 6—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Alcohol	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH^* kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^*$ e.u.	ΔG^* kcal mol ⁻¹
Allyl	18.17 ± 0.39	18.77 ± 0.40	20.01 ± 1.12	25.47 ± 0.18
Crotyl	18.67 ± 0.18	19.33 ± 0.17	18.32 ± 0.95	25.43 ± 0.17
Cinnamic	10.22 ± 0.10	10.90 ± 0.30	46.75 ± 0.70	26.70 ± 0.32

The entropy of activation is negative, indicating that activated complex is less probable and the rate will be slower. A constancy in free energy of activation ($\Delta G^*=26.1 \pm 0.6$ kcal mol⁻¹) suggests that probably a similar type of mechanism prevails. A plot of ΔH^* vs $-\Delta S^*$ is linear with β (isokinetic temperature) value of 283.6 K. Isokinetic temperature is less than the experimental range of temperature 323–348 K, indicating that the reaction is entropy controlled. Since ΔE values are in reverse order of reactivity, the oxidation is both energy and entropy controlled. A plot of ΔH^* vs $-\Delta S^*$ is linear, indicating that the same mechanism prevails in all cases.

The observed order of reactivity among alcohols studied is crotyl alcohol > allyl alcohol > cinnamic alcohol. This fact indicates that the methyl, an electron donating substituent, accelerates the reaction rate, while the phenyl, an electron attracting substituent, retards the process.

Mechanism: It is reported^{2,8,17} that in absence of a strong mineral acid, the various species of selenium dioxide that exist in aqueous acetic acid are HSeO₂⁺, H₂SeO₃ and AcHSeO₃, while in the presence of a strong mineral acid they are HSeO₂⁺, H₂SeO₃⁺ and AcH₂SeO₃⁺. Though HSeO₂⁺ is a stronger electrophile than H₂SeO₃, the former may not be present in sufficiently high concentration in

solution². Hence mechanism of oxidation by selenium dioxide in aqueous acetic acid should be considered in terms of H_2SeO_3 or $AcHSeO_3$ in absence of strong acid and $H_2SeO_3^+$ or $AcH_2SeO_3^+$ in the presence of a strong acid. The reaction between allylic alcohols and selenium dioxide failed to induce the polymerisation of added acrylonitrile, which indicates the absence of free radicals. The products of oxidation of allylic alcohols by selenium dioxide are unsaturated aldehydes, which rules out the possibility of attack of oxidising species on the double bond of these alcohols.

On the basis of above experimental facts, the proposed mechanism involves the reaction of selenious acid, H_2SeO_3 , with allylic alcohols (I) to form intermediate, allyl selenite (II), in a slow step. The latter on fast decomposition yields the aldehyde (III), the observed organic product. It is reported^{1,8} that selenium dioxide on reaction with alcohols forms alkyl selenites, which on decomposition yield corresponding aldehydes. In the present investigation, though no kinetic evidence regarding intermediate formation could be obtained, its formation can not be ruled out. The Michael-Menten's plot did not give intercept, indicating that the intermediate is not stable, that is, its formation constant would be extremely small to be kinetically determined.

Little can be said about the reality of hypo-selenious acid, H_2SeO_2 . There is no precedent for this species and if it forms, it must be much less stable than selenious acid, since the rate of oxidation does not decrease with time. Schaefer³ has also expressed similar views regarding the existence and stability of hyposelenious acid. Riley *et al.*^{1,9} have reported aldehydes as the products of oxidation of ethyl alcohol and benzyl alcohol by selenium dioxide.

Rate equation: On the basis of the proposed mechanism, the rate equation may be derived as follows.

The rate at which selenious acid reacts is

$$\frac{d}{dt}[H_2SeO_3] = k_1[\text{Alcohol}][H_2SeO_3] - k_{-1}[\text{allyl selenite}][H_2O]$$

and the rate at which product molecules are formed is

$$\frac{d}{dt}[\text{Product}] = k_2[\text{allyl selenite}]$$

Under steady conditions,

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[H_2SeO_3] = \frac{d}{dt}[\text{Product}]$$

The net rate of formation of allyl selenite is

$$\frac{d}{dt}[\text{allyl selenite}] = k_1[\text{alcohol}][H_2SeO_3] - k_{-1}[\text{allyl selenite}][H_2O] - k_2[\text{allyl selenite}]$$

At stationary state,

$$\frac{d}{dt}[\text{allyl selenite}] = 0$$

$$\text{Hence, } k_1[\text{alcohol}][H_2SeO_3] - k_{-1}[\text{allyl selenite}][H_2O] - k_2[\text{allyl selenite}] = 0$$

$$\text{or } [\text{allyl selenite}] = \frac{k_1[\text{alcohol}][H_2SeO_3]}{k_{-1}[H_2O] + k_2}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d}{dt}[H_2SeO_3] &= \frac{d}{dt}[\text{Product}] \\
 &= \frac{k_2 k_1 [\text{alcohol}][H_2SeO_3]}{k_{-1}[H_2O] + k_2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $k_2 \gg k_{-1}$,

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[H_2SeO_3] = k_1[\text{alcohol}][H_2SeO_3]$$

The derived rate equation explains the observed first order kinetics in both the substrate and the oxidant in absence of a strong acid.

Similarly, the rate equation for acid catalysed reaction may be derived by considering $H_2SeO_3^+$ as the reactive oxidising species.

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